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**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****GLOBAL ATLAS OF RENEWABLES ENERGIES: A COMPLEMENTARY
TO AN OPTIMAL ELECTRIFICATION PLANNING METHOD AT SHORT
AND LONG TERMS- CASE STUDY OF TOGO****Kabe Moyème*¹, Bokovi Yao², Kwami Senam Sedzro⁴, Marcel Aragah⁴, Takouda Pidéname⁵,
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ABSTRACT

The complementarity of renewable energy resources required for optimal electrification planning is of scientific and, above all, technical interest, to electrify a given region at any given time. With the aim of achieving one of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDG7), universal access to electricity at the lowest possible cost, studies have been carried out on the issue of optimal electrification planning in general throughout the world, and in Togo in particular. The first step was to produce an Atlas of Togo, and the second was to plan its electrification taking into account the least-cost technological options, while considering environmental integrity, energy reliability and guaranteeing access to electricity in off-grid areas. The approach proposed in this paper is based on Onset (Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool) combined with Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Onset is an open source python programming tool for optimal electrification planning. This approach takes into account the geographical, infrastructural and socio-economic characteristics of each region of the country. It can also be used to identify the various possible optimal models for electrification, especially in the choice of the most appropriate technologies according to available resources. The case of Togo is studied in this paper. Optimal electrification planning (different technologies such as grid extension, installation of isolated systems and/or microgrids...) is thus proposed, taking into account their costs (installation, production and operating costs...). Short-term (03 years and less) and long-term (15 years and more) studies for several scenarios (4) have been carried out. The results of these studies recommend, for low energy demands: in the case of rural areas (< 40 kWh/year per household) in the short term, stand-alone photovoltaic (PV) systems estimated at around 184 million USD with a production capacity of 20 MW. Finally, in the long term, we recommend stand-alone photovoltaic systems (USD 280 million with a production capacity of 62 MW), the strengthening of urban electrical resilience through grid extension systems (USD 964 million with a capacity of 274 MW), hydro mini-grid systems (USD 4 million with a production capacity of 1 MW) and PV-hybrid mini-grid systems (USD 1370 million with a production capacity of 0.72 GW).

KEYWORDS: Onset, optimal electrification, planning, renewable technologies energies, GIS systems

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context and issues

Energy is undoubtedly the main factor in a country's development; and for it to be sustainable, it requires a balance between supply and demand, and reliability [1][2]. The United Nations, through one of its main objectives: the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG7), recommends access to electrical energy for all [3][4] while respecting environmental constraints [5][6].

In fact, the global electrification rate is around 90 percent [7]; this electrification rate, if not fully achieved, would mean that only over a billion people have access to electricity. The continents whose populations have practically access to electricity are North America, North Africa and Europe, with a rate of 100% electrification; then come Latin America and the Caribbean (98 percent), Asia (98 percent), the Arab world (91 percent) and finally Sub-Saharan Africa, with a rate of 50.6 percent.

Africa, and Sub-Saharan Africa in particular, is currently the least electrified continent in the world, with half its population without access to electricity. This relatively low rate (50.6 percent) demonstrates that Africa remains the least developed continent in the world [8][9].

However, although a great deal of work has been undertaken [2][10] and despite the enormous efforts made by each country to achieve MDG7, universal access to electricity at the lowest cost, this rate is still very low, especially in rural areas [11]. The exponential growth of the population means that electricity needs are increasing [12][13] both in the short and, above all, in the long term.

Africa is the continent with the greatest potential for electrification [14]. The main primary energy sources for generating electricity are: uranium, coal, rivers and waterfalls, sea power, solar radiation, wind power and oil. Among these various primary resources, there are those that are renewable: rivers and waterfalls (production of hydraulic energy), solar radiation (production of solar energy), wind power (production of wind energy). To these renewable energies, we can add energy from plants and animal waste for the production of biomass energy.

So how is electrification evolving in Togo, and what are the strategies to be adopted for a genuine strategic plan for its electrification?

1.2 Context of Togo

Togo's electrification rate will rise from 55.7% in 2021 to 68% in 2022, compared with less than 20% in rural areas [15]. In recent years, the country has committed itself to achieving maximum electrification. The formulas used to calculate the coverage rate of electrified areas, the desservicing rate of electrified areas and the electrification rate, are respectively expressed by the equations (1.1), (1.2) and (1.3).

$$\tau_1 = \frac{\text{total number of potential subscribers in electrified areas}}{\text{total number of potential subscribers in Togo}} \quad (1.1)$$

$$\tau_2 = \frac{\text{total number of subscribers actually electrified}}{\text{total number of potential subscribers in electrified areas}} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_2}{\tau_1} \quad (1.3)$$

Figure 1 illustrates these rates. It shows the considerable efforts made by the country over the years to achieve full electrification.

Figure 1: Electrification rate in Togo

This rate, while high in urban areas and low in rural areas, demonstrates a willingness to move towards total electrification. Nonetheless, enormous efforts are still required in the short term, and above all in the long term, to achieve optimum, resilient electrification.

Figure 2 shows the country's internal production capacity with production units such as Contour Global, Amea and Kekeli; imports and consumption.

Figure 2: electrical loads

In this figure, the rate of external imports is 57%, compared with 43% for domestic production of electrical energy. This indicates the high level of dependence on external sources of electrical energy to meet the country's electrical loads. What will become of external constraints when loads increase over the years? Can we continue to rely heavily on external sources of electrical energy?

In addition, energy requirements vary dynamically, increasing not only over the course of a day or a month, but above all over the year as the population grows and matures. Figure 3 illustrates this increase.

Figure 3. Dynamic load variation

Figure 4. Annual peak variations

Figure 4 shows that, in addition to the annual variation in loads, peak demand has risen from 201 MW in 2018 to 273 MW in 2022, an increase of 35.8%. This exponential growth has led the country to build a Kekeli thermal power plant with a capacity of 47 MW and a Blitta solar power plant with a capacity of 50 MWp. Individual solar kits have also been introduced throughout the country for rural electrification.

However, questions remain as to how the country's main resources - solar, hydro, wind and biomass can be properly harnessed. And what about the electrical resilience of the future?

To answer these questions, electrification planning strategies are proposed in this article, to enable the country and other countries to plan or improve their electrification planning for the short and, above all, the long term, to achieve 100% access to electricity for all, as recommended by the UN in ODD7.

1.3 Bibliographical reviews

To increase the rate of access to electrical energy in developing countries, electrification planning is essential. Fernando Antonanzas-Torres et al. propose mini-grid systems for the electrification of African countries [16]. In this context, planning studies have been carried out in the literature, according to the specific issues addressed for each country. These include planning questions on extension cost, demand level [17][18], demand level, electricity price [19][20], demand level, extension criteria, PV cost [19][20][21], demand level, grid extension cost [22][23], demand level, discount rate [24][21], diesel cost, and demand level [25][26][27].

In summary, electrification planning work has been carried out in a number of countries such as: Liberia [28], Malawi [24], Nigeria [29][20], Burkina Faso [18], Ethiopia [30], Ghana [19][31], Senegal [32], Kenya [17], Tanzania [23], Liberia [28], Benin [33][34], South Africa [35][36], Sierra Leone [37], Cuba [38], Venezuela [39], Gabon [-], South Sudan [-], Guinea [-], Guinea Bissau [-], Madagascar [-], Niger [-], Somalia [-], . . and Togo [-].

The various planning studies in these countries are carried out using onsets, the open source python programming language. This approach alone, however, would require additional information to produce atlases of the various existing resources in order to better plan electrification and estimate the capacity of microgrids in each locality.

It is therefore necessary to propose a complementary scientific approach, to achieve partial or total electrification of countries in the process of total electrification, by opting for the valorization of available resources.

1.4 Scientific contribution

Many questions have arisen in the general context as to whether electrification can be fully achieved in countries where the rate of access to electricity is still low. In addition, Philipp A. et al [26], show that no study has been carried out in Togo or in other countries in the literature in terms of electrification strategy, unlike other countries which more or less present their electrification planning strategy.

To these issues and to the context of Philipp and al. this article brings a planning solution by presenting a scientific approach through a planning model coupling onset planning with the mapping of the different resources that may exist on the territory. This work thus proposes a new approach to optimal planning for effective electrification of off-grid areas. It enables us to :

- provide information on the various electrification technologies based on the open source python programming approach onset for optimal electrification planning
- produce a global atlas of energy resources
- provide information on microgrid capacity in each locality

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Planning method

The method is based on the onset model, an open source programming algorithm using spatial data, and adapted to the study context. The electrification planning model therefore takes into account: the minimization of system costs (operating costs, investment costs, maintenance costs), the evolution and level of the population, and the different configurations of technologies according to resource availability and cost. The mathematical formulation of the model, inspired by [40], is then presented. It is a partial equilibrium model based on a linear optimization problem whose objective is to minimize the total cost of power systems in order to satisfy energy demand. This optimization is performed in a general way, depending on the technology, period and region of interest, in order to minimize the project cost.

$$\min: \left\{ inv + \sum_{t=1}^{n-1} \frac{C_{o\&M} + C_{bat,r} + Ft}{(1+r)^t} \right\} \quad (1.4)$$

$$inv = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_e C_{tech}^u P_{tech}^T + C_{bat} C_s \quad (1.5)$$

$$tech = \{solar, wind, hydraulic, biomass, \dots\}$$

$$\alpha_e = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the technology is available} \\ 0, & \text{if not} \end{cases} \quad (1.6)$$

Where inv is the investment; t , the duration; $C_{o\&M}$, the cost of operation and maintenance; $C_{bat,r}$, the cost of replacement batteries; r is the discount rate; Ft : fuel expenditure; n : system lifetime; C_{tech}^u , the unit cost of each technology P_{tech}^T , the total production (capacity) of each technology; C_{bat} , the cost of battery capacity and, finally, C_s , the battery storage capacity.

The final electricity cost LCOE (USD/kWh) required for the project, depending on the investment cost, production cost E_t , and discount rate, is defined by :

$$LCOE(t) = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{n-1} \frac{I_t + O\&M_t + Ft}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^{n-1} \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}} \quad (1.7)$$

It should be noted that this LCOE(t) function, which represents the cost of electricity, varies with time. In West Africa, for example, it averages 0.35 USD/ kWh. [16].

For this study, the planning modeling diagram is shown in Figure 5.

RE : Renewable Energies

Figure 5: Diagram of the electrification planning model

Following this planning approach, scenarios are generated.

2.2 Scenario generation

Scenario generation is based not only on population over the years, but also on time-dependent electricity generation investment costs. The corresponding scenario generation diagram is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Scenario generation diagram

Four scenarios are obtained from this generation. Scenarios 1 and 2 reflect short-term investments, with a relatively low current population and relatively high technology costs. Scenarios 3 and 4, on the other hand, reflect the long term, with a growing population and a relatively higher or lower cost of technology. The results of these different scenarios are shown in figures 7, 8, 9 and 10.

2.3 Formation of microgrid capacities

The formation of microgrid capacity is highly dependent on population density and, above all, on the level of demand for electrification. Table 1 shows estimated consumption levels in kWh according to population consumption capacity levels.

Table 1: Tier or consumption levels [25]:

Niveau	Tier 1	Tier 2	Tier 3	Tier 4	Tier 5
Per capita consumption (kWh/an)	8	44	160	423	598

The level of electrification allows us to evaluate the population's demand for electrification. This demand for electrification DE is given by equation (18):

$$DE = \text{Densité de population} \times \text{Tier} \tag{1.8}$$

The various results obtained are presented.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results of electrification planning in Togo

3.3.1 Short-term case

The estimated planning results for the short term are shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7: Electrification, scenario 1

Figure 8: Electrification, scenario 2

For the short term, two scenarios are generated: scenarios 1 and 2. For scenario 1, the approach proposes a selected distribution for the north of the country and towards its southern part. Technologies such as stand-alone photovoltaic (PV) systems are proposed. For scenario 2, on the other hand, and opting for a higher cost, hybrid PV mini-grids and a few hydraulic mini-grids are recommended for almost total distribution throughout the country.

So what are the long-term results?

3.1.2 Long-term case

The long-term results of scenarios 3 and 4 are shown in figures 9 and 10 :

Figure 9: Electrification scenario 3

Figure 10: Electrification scenario 4

In this case study, the extension of the network in urban areas is recommended as a first step, and autonomous systems are chosen as a low-cost technology option. However, for total electrification of the country, all technological options are possible. In addition to stand-alone systems and grid extension, the results of scenario 4 also include mini-grids such as hydraulic mini-grids and hybrid mini-grids based on a combination of available natural resources. In fact, the approach focuses more on solar and hydraulic energy. It should be noted that the country also has other potential energy sources, such as biomass and wind power, which could also provide technological options for electrical resilience in certain regions of the country: hence the complementary atlas.

The results of the different scenarios are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of scenario results

Year	2024-2030				2030-2050			
	8.095.498				> 15 000 000			
Population Scenarios	Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Scenario 3		Scenario 4	
technologies	Capacity (MW)	investissement (million USD)	capacity	inv	Capacity (MW)	inv	capacity (MW)	inv
Extension	-	-	-	-	1	236	274	964
Stand-alone PV systems	20	184	-	-	24	220	62	280
Mini-grid PV hybrid	-	-	320	564	-	-	720	1371
Mini-grid hydraulic	-	-	-	1.12	-	-	1	4.42
wind and diesel mini-grids	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

inv = investment (in million USD)

Table 2 shows the results of the different scenarios for both the short and long term. For the short term, i.e. scenarios 1 and 2, stand-alone photovoltaic systems are recommended with a capacity of 20 MW, estimated at 184 million USD. Scenario 2 opts for hybrid PV mini-grids with a capacity of 320 MW at a cost of 567 million USD, versus hydraulic mini-grids estimated at 1.12 million USD. In summary, for the short term and depending on the technological options chosen, two proposals are made: isolated systems, and network systems with capacities in line with the population rate. On the other hand, for the long term and with an increasing population, PV systems are proposed with a capacity of 24 MW for scenario 3 versus 62 MW for scenario 4, with respective investments of USD 220 million and USD 280 million. The investment cost of grid extension during these periods requires 236 million for a total capacity of 1 MW; mini-grids are also included to ensure electrical resilience at an estimated total cost of 1374 million USD for 721 MW. On the other hand, scenario 4 shows the possibility of achieving total electrification of the country, estimating a global capacity of 1.06 GW for an investment of 2.6 billion USD. The approach also proposes a grid extension of the order of USD 964 million in urban areas, with a capacity of 274 MW.

Maps of the various natural resources are shown.

3.2 Mapping natural resources: Atlas of Togo

3.2.1 Natural resources map

Figures 11, 12, 13 and 14 show various maps of the country's renewable natural resources, including solar, biomass, hydro and wind power.

[Moyeme* *et al.*, 12(11): November, 2023]
 ICTM Value: 3.00

As can be seen from these figures, there is a non-uniform distribution of these resources across the country. It provides more information on the possibility of combining these natural resources to ensure the country's electrical reliability.

3.2.2 Atlas of natural resources and microgrid formation capacities

The non-uniform distribution of natural resources has enabled us to present a global map of these resources in figure 15. Figure 16 shows the capacity for microgrid formation across the territory.

Figure 15: natural resources atlas

Figure 16: microgrid capacity atlas

In fact, these two figures are complementary in that they not only provide a simpler reading of the location of natural resource availability and capacity, but also provide information on the potential for microgrid formation in these localities.

The various results of potential microgrid formation are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Estimated allocation of energy demand in Togo

Togo electrification request	Minimal population		Tier	Daily request	Monthly request	Annual request
For Prefecture	level 3 (high)	> 150 000	4	> 66 MWh	> 2 GWh	> 24 GWh
	level 2 (medium)	[90 000 - 150 000]	3	[2- 66] MWh	[0.06 - 2] GWh	[0.72 - 24] GWh
	level 1 (weak)	< 90 000	1	< 2 MWh	< 60 MWh	< 720 MWh
For township	< 20 000		1	< 100 kWh	< 3 MWh	< 160 MWh
For village	< 1 000		1	< 20 kWh	< 600 kWh	< 8 MWh

The results in this table present estimates of electrical energy demand according to population density by village, canton and prefecture of the country. For populations of less than 1,000, the estimated monthly capacity is 600 kWh, while for larger populations of less than 20,000, it is less than 3 MWh. In general, the higher the population value, the higher the estimated consumption, reflecting the expected capacity data.

Discussions

The different results obtained and presented enable us to make a scientific contribution to the planning of electrification in developing countries, and to contribute to the decision-making process for political decision-makers. Indeed, in the Togolese context, it has been shown that the strong growth in loads over the years has created enormous needs in terms of electrical energy, and the high level of external dependence has raised scientific questions about how to make the most of the country's main existing natural resources for the benefit of the country. Planning has therefore enabled us to propose, for different scenarios, the most advantageous technologies in the short and long term, in order to optimally plan the electrification of the country.

In the short term, therefore, the initial focus is on stand-alone photovoltaic systems, concentrating on off-grid rural areas to achieve 80% electrification by 2024-2030. However, photovoltaic systems alone remain very limited, especially in the rainy season, as their potential is very low. Monthly solar mapping results were obtained and presented by Amou *et al* [41], showing the different solar potential in different months. Indeed, low solar potential during unfavorable periods would limit photovoltaic efficiency and consequently lead to electrical imbalances. It would be scientifically and technically sensible to create an energy network to ensure the permanent continuity of electrical energy.

Furthermore, by opting for high-cost technologies, the approach advocates mini-grid systems such as hydraulic mini-grids and PV hybrid mini-grids. These technologies not only make it possible to exploit the various existing

hybrid resources, but also ensure electrical resilience in the event of unfavorable resource periods. An optimum network model should be recommended in this respect, to be studied and developed with the aim of facilitating this network management.

In the short term, therefore, to partially ensure the electrification of off-grid areas, the country has two advantages, with investments estimated at USD 184 million and USD 565.12 million respectively, for a capacity of around 20 MW and 320 MW respectively. In the short term, therefore, it would be advisable to opt first for stand-alone isolated systems for faster electrification. Then, in a second phase, to interconnect these systems in order to set up electrical networks for perfect electrical resilience, to ensure balance between supply and demand.

However, to achieve total electrification, the country will need to take all technologies into account for the long term: extended grid systems, autonomous photovoltaic systems, hydraulic mini-grids and PV hybrids, for electrical resilience. It should also be noted that wind and biomass technologies have not been generated by the approach: this shows that these technologies have either not been taken into account or have been downplayed. The results of the mappings thus carried out show significant wind and biomass potential, which could constitute alternative resources in the realization of the proposed mini-grid systems. Furthermore, salami *et al* [42][43] have shown in their study that, with the development of adapted aerogenerator technologies, it would be possible to exploit this wind resource, whose speed is relatively low (4 m/s), for small-scale applications. This is particularly true in southern and northern Togo, where average wind power is around 40 W/m² (see figure 14). As for biomass, the country's Plateaux region has enormous potential for producing electrical energy. Animal waste, which is not negligible in the country's various pastures, is also an asset for the production of electrical energy (biogas). All these resources need to complement each other, and the distribution of their potential across the country would enable us to make optimal energy combinations for mini-grids.

4. CONCLUSION

Taking into account the totality of the country's various natural resources is essential for optimal planning of electrification. This study presented a scientific approach to combining planning approaches with an atlas of available resources, in order to better manage planning. Togo was studied for the strategic implementation of its total electrification by 2050, and the results obtained were conclusive. Indeed, the initial results show the country's high energy dependence on the outside world, since most of the country's electrical energy is imported. To ensure its energy independence, the planning results obtained recommend two solutions for partial or total electrification of the country in the short and long term. In the short term, the country should opt for autonomous photovoltaic systems to achieve a reasonable rate of electrification by 2030. In the same context, a mini-grid system is also proposed as an option for high-cost technologies. To achieve full electrification by 2050, all technological options are proposed, such as stand-alone PV systems, grid extension systems, hybrid and non-hybrid mini-grid systems with a total cost of 2.62 billion USD and a total production capacity of 1.1 GW. It has also been shown that solar and wind power, in addition to being intermittent sources, are temporarily available depending on the season. The same is true of hydropower and biomass, hence the importance of the recommended complementarity of natural resources. Not only would this complementarity enable the integration of all the different existing natural resources for electrical reliability, it would also contribute more to environmental protection than exploited fossil resources. Ultimately, this article makes a contribution to the scientific approach needed for decision-making on optimal electrification planning for off-grid areas.

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